

Terpenoids and Related Compounds : Part IX¹. Chemical Investigation of *Euphorbia sikkimensis*, Boiss.

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Glut-5en-3one, butyrospermol, β -sitosterol, 1-hexacosanol and a new triterpene, $C_{31}H_{52}O$, have been isolated from *E. sikkimensis*, Boiss.

Euphorbia sikkimensis, Boiss² belonging to the *Euphorbiaceae* family is a perennial shrub, which grows in the Himalayas at an altitude of 8000 to 10,000 ft. and also in the Sikkim Himalayas. We became interested to undertake a chemical investigation of the whole plant since no work was reported in the literature. The neutral material from the benzene extract was chromatographed over deactivated alumina. The less polar fraction from the chromatogram was identified as glut-5en-3one³, m.p. 238–40°, $[\alpha]_D + 39^\circ$.

The more polar fraction was found to be a mixture of two triterpenes : butyrospermol⁴, m.p. 110–11°, $[\alpha]_D - 11.5^\circ$ and a new triterpene, $C_{31}H_{52}O$, m.p. 94–6°, $[\alpha]_D + 58.6^\circ$ ($M^+ 440$). This new triterpene had no U-V absorption between the range 220–330 μ , I.R. peak at $\nu_{max}^{CHO^3}$ 3600 cm^{-1} showed the presence of one hydroxyl group. Perbenzoic acid titration on the acetate showed the presence of one double bond. NMR also showed a peak at 4.75 ppm indicating the presence of two vinyl protons as = CH_2 groups and a peak at 3.2 ppm showed the presence of one hydroxyl proton. The acetate, m.p. 107–8°, $[\alpha]_D + 50^\circ$, on acid isomerisation gave a product, $C_{33}H_{54}O_2$, m.p. 149–50°. From the above it can be concluded that the new compound is probably a pentacyclic triperpene. Further work on this new triterpene was interrupted as we failed to isolate the same compounds from the same plant collected from another source and at a different seasons. From the latter, however we could isolate 1-hexacosanol⁵, $C_{26}H_{54}O$, m.p. 79°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$. The most polar fraction was found to be β -sitosterol identified as its acetate.

It is important to mention here that from our experience with the plant, we found that the nature of the compound and the yield varies with season and altitude at which the plant is obtained.

The melting points are uncorrected. Petroleum used had a boiling range 60–80°. All the rotations were taken in chloroform unless and otherwise stated.

1. Part VIII. Terpenoids and related compounds. H. N. Khastgir, B. P. Pradhan and D. R. Misra. Communicated to this journal.
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3. Chapon and David, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1953, 333.
4. Sir Ian Heilbron, E. R. H. Jones and P. A. Robins, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 444.
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EXPERIMENTAL

Dried and powdered whole plant (960 g, collected in winter season) was extracted with benzene for 30 hr. Benzene was distilled off and the residual resinous mass was taken up in ether. The ether solution was washed with 10% NaOH solution and then with water. The neutral ether solution dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated when a gummy residue (16.0 g) was obtained.

The above gummy residue was chromatographed over a column of alumina (640 g, deactivated with 25.4 ml of 10% aq. acetic acid). On elution with light petroleum a crystalline solid A, m.p. 220–28° (1.0 g.) was obtained. Further elution with light petroleum : benzene (4 : 1) gave a solid B, m.p. 80–85° (0.6 g.). Petroleum : benzene (3 : 2) eluted another solid C, m.p. 125–32° (0.8 g.).

Examination of solid A : Glut-5en-3one : The first crop of the crystalline solid (1.0 g) on repeated crystallisation from chloroform and methanol gave a crystalline solid m.p. 238–40°, $[\alpha]_D + 39^\circ$, I.R. peak at 1707 cm^{-1} . This was identified as glut-5en-3one with an authentic sample (m.m.p. and I.R.) (Lit.³ m.p. 247, $[\alpha]_D + 31^\circ$) (Found : C, 84.74; H, 11.31. Calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}$: C, 84.84; H, 11.39%).

LAH reduction of glut-5en-3one : Glut-5en-3 α -ol : Glut-5en-3one (0.15) was refluxed with LAH (0.075 g) in dry ether (25 ml) for 4 hrs. The mixture was cooled and a saturated solution of sodium sulphate was added, extracted with ether, washed with water, dried and ether removed to give a solid, m.p. 190–92°. This on crystallisation from chloroform and methanol afforded fine crystals, m.p. 196–7°, $[\alpha]_D + 57^\circ$ (Lit.³ m.p. 195–6°, $[\alpha]_D + 59.5^\circ$) (Found : C, 84.36; H, 11.76. Calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$: C, 84.44; H, 11.81%).

Glut-5en-3 α -yl acetate : Glut-5en-3 α -ol (0.1 g) was acetylated with pyridine (1 ml) and acetic anhydride (1 ml) by keeping over water bath for 4 hrs. The reaction product was worked up as usual, and the solid obtained, m.p. 225–7°, on crystallisation from chloroform and methanol furnished crystals, m.p. 231–3°, $[\alpha]_D + 46^\circ$. This was found to be identical with an authentic specimen of glut-5en-3 α -yl acetate (m.m.p. and I.R.) (Lit.³ 235–6°, $[\alpha]_D + 41.5^\circ$) (Found : C, 81.82; H, 11.15. Calc. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$: C, 81.99; H, 11.18%).

Examination of solid B : Isolation of a new triterpene I : The solid B on repeated chromatography and fractional crystallisations from methanol afforded fine needle-shaped crystals I, m.p. 95–96°, $[\alpha]_D + 58.6^\circ$. There was no U-V absorption between the range 220–300 μ , I.R. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{CHCl}_3}$ 3600 cm^{-1} (hydroxyl group). (Found : C, 84.50; H, 11.78. $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}$ requires : C, 84.54; H, 11.82%), (M^+ 440).

Acetylation of I : I (0.1 g) was acetylated with pyridine (1 ml) and acetic anhydride (1 ml) by heating on water bath for 4 hrs. The product was worked up as usual and the solid obtained (0.1 g) was chromatographed over alumina (10 g, deactivated with 0.4 ml of aq. acetic acid 10%). Petroleum eluted a solid which on crystallisation from methanol gave crystals, m.p. 107–8°, $[\alpha]_D + 50^\circ$ (Found : C, 82.10; H, 11.11. $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_2$ requires, C, 82.16; H, 11.20%).

Benzoate of I : I (0.1 g) was benzoylated with pyridine (1 ml) and benzoyl chloride (1 ml) by heating on water bath for 4 hrs. The reaction product (0.1 g) obtained on working up in the usual manner was chromatographed over alumina (10 g., deactivated with 0.4 ml. of 10% aq. acetic acid). Petroleum eluted an oily solid which on crystallisation from methanol and keeping for overnight furnished needle-shaped crystals of benzoate of I, m.p. 274–5° (Found : C, 83.74; H, 10.12. $C_{38}H_{56}O_2$ requires : C, 83.82; H, 10.29%).

CrO₃/Py oxidation of I : I (0.1 g) dissolved in pyridine (1 ml) was added to a complex prepared from CrO₃ (0.1 g.) and pyridine (1 ml) at 10° and allowed to come to room temperature overnight. On working up in the usual way a solid product (0.075 g) was obtained, which was chromatographed over alumina (10 g., deactivated with 0.4 ml of 10% aq. acetic acid). Petroleum eluted a solid which on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol gave crystals, m.p. 103–4°, $[\alpha]_D + 27.1^\circ$. (Found : C, 84.84; H, 11.31. $C_{31}H_{50}O$ requires : C, 84.93; H, 11.41%).

Isolation of Butyrospermol : The mother liquors of the alcohol I were combined and dried (0.3 g) and then acetylated as usual with pyridine (3 ml) and acetic anhydride (3 ml). The solid obtained on working up the reaction mixture was chromatographed over alumina (25 g., deactivated with 1 ml of 10% sq. acetic acid). The solid obtained from the petroleum eluents was crystallised several times from methanol. The mother liquors on standing for three days furnished long needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 141–3°, $[\alpha]_D + 14.2^\circ$. This was identified as butyrospermol acetate by comparison with an authentic sample (m.m.p. and I.R.). (Lit.⁴ m.p. 146.5–7.5°, $[\alpha]_D + 11^\circ$) (Found : C, 81.72; H, 10.09. Calc. for $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.99; H, 11.18%).

Hydrolysis of butyrospermol acetate to Butyrospermol : To the above acetate (0.1 g) dissolved in benzene (5 ml) was added 5% methanolic KOH (25 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 4 hrs. This was worked up as usual and the product chromatographed over alumina (10 g., deactivated with 0.4 ml of 10% aq. acetic acid). Petroleum : benzene (3 : 2) eluted a solid which on crystallisation from methanol gave crystals, m.p. 110–11°, $[\alpha]_D - 11.50^\circ$ (Lit.⁴ m.p. 111–13°, $[\alpha]_D - 12^\circ$) (Found : C, 84.34; H, 11.76. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}O$: C, 84.44; H, 11.81%).

Butyrospermol benzoate : To butyrospermol (0.1 g) dissolved in pyridine (1 ml) was added benzoyl chloride (1 ml) and the mixture heated on a water bath for 4 hrs. After working up in the usual manner the crude benzoate was chromatographed over alumina (10 g., deactivated with 0.4 ml of 10% aq. acetic acid). Elution with petroleum afforded a solid which on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol furnished crystals, m.p. 130–32°, $[\alpha]_D + 32.6^\circ$, identified as butyrospermol benzoate by comparison with an authentic specimen (m.m.p. and I.R.) (Lit.⁴ m.p. 130–33°, $[\alpha]_D + 29.3^\circ$). (Found : C, 83.65; H, 10.16. Calc. for $C_{37}H_{54}O_2$: C, 83.72; H, 10.25%).

Dried and powdered whole plant (960 g.) of *E. sikkimensis* collected during rainy season was extracted with benzene for 30 hrs and was worked up as described above. The neutral gummy residue (10 g.) obtained was chromatographed over alumina (40 g., deactivated with 16 ml of 10% aq. acetic acid). Petroleum eluted a solid, D, m.p. 60–70°, and petroleum : benzene (3 : 2) eluted another solid E, m.p. 132°, identical with solid C (m.m.p.) described above.

Examination of solid D : 1-hexacosanol : Solid D on crystallisation several times from methanol afforded crystals, m.p. 79–80°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$, I.E. $\nu_{max}^{CHCl_3}$ 3350 cm^{-1} (OH group) identical with 1-hexacosanol in all respects (Lit.⁵ m.p. 79° $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$) (Found : C, 81.64; H, 14.11. Calc. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}$: C, 81.65; H, 14.13%) (mol wt. Rast method 376). The acetate prepared in the usual manner (pyridine-acetic anhydride method) had m.p. 68–9°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$ identical with 1-hexacosanyl acetate (Lit.⁵ m.p. 65°).

Examination of solid C : β -sitosterol : The solid C after chromatography and several crystallisations afforded crystals, m.p. 132–3°, $[\alpha]_D - 35^\circ$. The acetate prepared by the usual method had m.p. 124–6°, $[\alpha]_D - 34^\circ$, identical with authentic β -sitosterol acetate (m.m.p. and I.R.).

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